

Dual Luminescence of Phenothiazine in 2-Methylbutane

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Ground state dimerisation and simultaneous photostudy of the monomer-dimer system in solution phase, particularly for planar (or near planar) molecules has drawn the attention of photochemists since mid of this century¹. Benzene, anthracene, 7-azaindole (7AI), 1-azacarbazole (1AC) are among the various studied systems²⁻⁶. The proposed structure of the dimer depends on the system concerned. Thus, for benzene and anthracene, the dimer is a sandwich one (now a T-shaped or a distorted sandwich structure is preferred)³, while for 7AI or 1AC an end-to-end doubly hydrogen-bonded dimer is generally accepted⁴⁻⁶. Excited state double proton transfer from the photoexcited dimer (as a consequence of the ground state dimerisation) has also been established for the latter compounds⁴⁻⁶.

The present communication reports the ground state dimerisation of a new system, viz. phenothiazine (PTN) in 2-methylbutane (2MB). From the absorption as well as steady-state and nanosecond time-resolved emission studies, it is established that both monomer and dimer of PTN are present in the ground state and the two species are in equilibrium. The two distinct emissions have been associated to the monomeric and dimeric species. It has also been argued that the excited state proton transfer reaction does not play any role with the present system.

Results and Discussion

Absorption and excitation spectra: The room temperature (25°) absorption spectra of phenothiazine (PTN) in 2-methylbutane (2MB) consists of a broad band having maximum at around 310 nm. With increase in PTN concentration, the optical density increases but not according to Beer's law pointing to the formation of associated (dimeric or even oligomeric) species in the ground state. No new absorption was, however, noticed. This might be due to the fact that the monomer and dimer (or oligomer) do not differ appreciably in absorption⁶. The excitation spectra, however, show two different bands (maxima at ≈ 290 and ≈ 320 nm) corresponding to the two emissions of PTN (Fig. 1). This reflects clearly the presence of two ground state species (see later). Since the dilute solution gives principally the 290 nm excitation and the 320 nm band develops at higher concentrations, the monomer is supposed to absorb at higher and the dimer (or oligomer) at lower energy. Thus a change in solution concentration is expected to change the band shape in the absorption spectrum of PTN. A

Fig. 1. Excitation spectra of 5×10^{-4} M PTN in 2MB monitored at (a) 345 and (b) 440 nm emissions (peak heights were matched by mathematical manipulation)

closer scrutiny, however, reflects that the absorption spectra cover both the excitation bands near its broad maximum and hence no appreciable change in band pattern can be observed with an increase in solution concentration.

The deviation from Beer's law at higher concentrations of PTN solutions in 2MB provides a way to establish that the ground state reaction is actually monomer-dimer association (thus negating the formation of oligomers) as well as to determine the equilibrium constant for the process. To start with, let us assume the reaction to be monomer-dimer interconversion. The equilibrium expression can be written as

$$K = \frac{[D]}{[M]^2} = \frac{C - [M]}{2[M]^2} \quad (1)$$

where, K is the dimerisation constant, $[M]$ and $[D]$ are the molar concentration of monomer and dimer respectively, and C is the actual concentration of PTN in the solution. Since at sufficiently high energy (285 nm) the absorption is due principally to the monomer, we can write

$$A = \epsilon [M] l \quad (2)$$

where, A is the absorbance at 285 nm, ϵ the molar extinction coefficient of the monomer at the same wavelength

and l the pathlength. Combining the two equations and taking $l = 1$ cm, one obtains

$$\frac{C}{A} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \left(\frac{2K}{\epsilon^2} \right) A \quad (3)$$

Linearity of C/A against A confirms the formation of 1 : 1 association and validates the starting assumption of dimer formation. Formation of higher oligomers is thus rejected. The equilibrium constant for the dimerisation process comes out to be $107 M^{-1}$ at the experimental temperature. This corresponds to a ΔG value of -2.8 kcal mol $^{-1}$. A parallel way of establishing the dimerisation has been provided by Ingham and El-Bayoumi⁵ where they considered the long wavelength absorption and ascribed it principally to the dimer. The large ΔG value suggests that the dimer is probably stabilised through hydrogen bonding. From the molecular structure of PTN, a doubly hydrogen-bonded sandwich structure can tentatively be proposed for the dimeric species (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Proposed structure of PTN dimer

Fluorescence spectra : Dilute solution ($1 \times 10^{-5} M$) of PTN in 2MB exhibits a fluorescence band with a maximum near 340 nm and this is attributed to the normal emission (F_1) of the monomer. The corresponding excitation spectrum shows a maximum at ≈ 290 nm. In addition to the normal one, concentrated solutions of PTN give rise to a second fluorescence (F_2) with a peak at around 430 nm (Fig. 3). A new excitation band ($\lambda_{\text{max}} \approx 320$ nm) corresponding to this emission in conjunction with the above discussion indicates that it is originating directly from the excitation of the ground state PTN-dimer. The slight redshift of F_1 peak at higher concentrations of PTN might be the consequence of reabsorption due to the dimer. This is again corroborated from the excitation spectrum corresponding to the F_2 emission, showing that there is really an absorption near 320 nm (Fig. 1).

The decay analysis of PTN solution in 2MB (0.1 mM) using the time-correlated single-photon counting technique gives lifetime values 12 and 1.6 nanoseconds corresponding to the monomer and dimer fluorescence respectively. The reduced lifetime for the dimer is a very common observation and reflects the enhanced nonradiative decay through greater number of coupled vibronic modes. The τ values hardly depend on the concentration of the solution. The relative abundance of the short-lived species, however, goes on increasing as one gradually increases the λ_{exc} from

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of (a) 1×10^{-5} , (b) 1×10^{-4} , (c) 5×10^{-4} and (d) $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions of PTN in 2MB ($\lambda_{\text{exc.}} = 290$ nm).

290 to 320 nm reflecting once again that the excited species corresponds to the ground state dimer having a red-shifted excitation band.

Since the proposed ground state dimer is probably hydrogen bonded, there remains a possibility for the excited state prototropic reaction to take part. But the following discussion suggests that excited state proton transfer (ESPT) reaction is not responsible for the F_2 emission. Firstly, the excitation spectrum corresponding to the F_2 band has a mirror relationship to the emission. This indicates that F_2 originates directly from the dimer. Secondly, both F_1 and F_2 have been observed in solvents like 2-methylbutane (nonpolar, aprotic), acetonitrile (polar, aprotic) and ethanol (polar, protic) as well although the relative intensities differ in different solvents⁷. Had the F_2 emission been due to the excited state intramolecular proton transfer, it would have been restricted to the non-polar solvents. The proposed centrosymmetric structure (Fig. 2) of the dimer also suggests that photoexcitation does not change the dipolar character of the ground state species indicating insignificant chance of ESPT.

The relative intensities of F_2 and F_1 depend on the concentration of the solution as well as the excitation energy. F_2/F_1 goes on increasing with rise in concentration till $10^{-3} M$ (highest concentration studied). This can very reasonably be related to the increase in dimer population in concentrated solutions. At room temperature, as we move from excitation wavelength 270 to 335 nm in steps. F_2/F_1 goes on increasing. Fig. 4 shows the plot of relative yield of F_2 to F_1 against excitation energy. The curve clearly shows two plateaus. The plateaus correspond to the excitation, basically, of a single species. The curve has the highest slope at an excitation energy where there is maximum

Fig 4 Plot of F_2/F_1 vs excitation energy for 1×10^{-4} M PTN in 2MB overlap of the two excitation bands. Thus one can in principle record either of the two fluorescences almost exclusively by proper choice of the solution concentration and excitation wavelength.

The above discussion leads to the following points : (i) in 2MB solution, phenothiazine monomer remains in equilibrium with its dimer, (ii) on selective photoexcitation both monomer and dimer fluorescence but at different energy and the fluorescence lifetimes differ appreciably and (iii) ESPT plays no role with the present system.

Experimental

Phenothiazine (Fluka) was purified by recrystallisation from 90% ethanol and by vacuum sublimation and finally by recrystallisation from absolute ethanol. Purity of the compound was checked by spectroscopic methods as well as by tlc. Spectragrade (Aldrich) 2-methylbutane was used as received.

Absorption and emission spectra of the aerated solutions were recorded in a Shimadzu MPS-2000 spectrophotometer and a Spex fluorolog-2 spectrofluorometer respectively. For lifetime measurement, time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) technique was adopted⁸; a nanosecond spectrofluorometer (Edinburgh Instruments 199 fluorescence spectrometer) was used and the data from ORTEC 7100 multichannel analyser were analysed in a HCL PC-AT microcomputer (IBM compatible)⁹.

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